

Specialist leisure activities for children with disabilities: The impact on family well-being at an individual, family, and community level

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Family carers of children with disabilities report both positive and negative aspects of family life, and many experience significant mental health concerns. Specialist leisure activities can improve the emotional well-being of these children, although the wider effects on their families remain unclear. This study examined how specialist leisure clubs for children with disabilities influence the well-being of family members, including parents and siblings. Ten children aged six to seventeen attended specialist leisure clubs in dedicated children's centres. They participated for one and a half to two hours each week or for two to four hours every fortnight, independent of their parents. These children could not access mainstream leisure clubs because they required high levels of support related to communication, behaviour, and personal care. The clubs offered one to one support and activities that included child-led play, sports, arts, and group games. Interviews and focus groups were carried out with 12 family carers between June and October 2023. Data were examined through reflexive thematic analysis. Impacts on family well-being emerged at individual, family, and community levels. Individually, family carers gained opportunities for guilt free breaks from caring responsibilities. At the family level, participants reported reduced distress about their child or sibling and noticed strengthened relationships between parents and within parent and sibling relationships. At the community level, participants described a sense of inclusion through meeting other families and receiving peer support. These findings suggest that specialist leisure activities may enhance family resilience during a period of increasing pressure on carers of children with disabilities.

Keywords: caregiving; children with disabilities; family resilience; leisure activities; well-being

The proportion of children identified as disabled, defined as having physical or mental impairments that create long term negative effects on daily life (National Health Service, 2024), has almost doubled over the past decade (Kirk-Wade, 2024). Families who care for children and young people with disabilities face considerable and increasing challenges. Their caring responsibilities can limit the time available for social or leisure activities and can also create financial pressure. In 2022 these families faced an average of £583 in extra costs each month. Under these conditions family carers are vulnerable to mental health problems, with 87% reporting such difficulties and only one in five receiving adequate support from service providers (Disabled Children's Partnership, 2023).

Despite the recognised positive aspects of caring for a child with a disability, including opportunities to build social connections through support groups, shared enjoyment during activities, feelings of accomplishment, a greater appreciation of life, and increased empathy towards others (Luijckx et al., 2019; Yoong & Koritsas, 2012), caregiving is still frequently associated with negative impacts on families. Families of children with disabilities often experience poorer physical and mental health related quality of life (Vonneilich et al., 2014). These difficulties may arise from factors such as time consuming caregiving responsibilities, social isolation, or the stigma surrounding disabilities. For instance, caregiving can restrict parents' opportunities to form relationships, spend quality time with partners or other relatives, or take part in leisure activities (Yoong & Koritsas, 2012).

To address the caregiving burden, it is important to identify interventions that can improve family well-being. One such intervention is respite care, in which trained professionals temporarily relieve carers of their responsibilities, allowing them to engage in other activities or rest (Kiernozeck, 2015). Respite care has been demonstrated to reduce psychological, emotional, financial, and physical burdens of caregiving; however, carers may encounter barriers to accessing respite services, including reluctance to accept help or challenges in finding services tailored to their family's specific requirements (Ling, 2012). For respite care to be effective, it must be person-centred and responsive to individual needs, although this can be difficult for providers to achieve consistently.

Short breaks are another possible intervention to improve the well-being of families of children with disabilities. These programmes offer activities for children with disabilities, ranging from a few hours to several days, often at specialised centres or community facilities. Research has indicated that short breaks can reduce carer stress, improve family dynamics, and enhance overall family well-being (Bautista et al., 2018; Robertson et al., 2011).

Leisure activities, defined as non-mandatory activities for enjoyment, relaxation or enrichment, offer another avenue for improving family well-being (Mansfield et al., 2020). Shared leisure activities, in which parents and children participate together, can strengthen parent-child relationships by fostering closeness and reducing conflict (Simić & Durašin, 2020; Zabidi et al., 2023). To maximise benefits of leisure to family well-being, social support for parents should be offered simultaneously to allow them to better meet their children's needs during active leisure (Stiller & Stiller, 2024).

Children with disabilities experience barriers to accessing leisure in mainstream environments. It has been reported that 55% of parents did not enrol their children in leisure services because the services were inaccessible for their child's needs (Personnel Today, 2008). According to family-carers of children with disabilities, there is a lack of understanding of their children's needs among leisure staff (Thompson & Emira, 2011). Also, mainstream leisure environments often exclude children with disabilities as they may not be able to participate in activities preferred by their non-disabled peers, and staff and other children can hold implicit ableist views regarding their abilities and impairments, creating an "us-and-them" situation (Hodge & Runswick-Cole, 2013).

One potential avenue for alleviating the burden of care on families and improving their well-being is specialist leisure provision, tailored to the needs of children with disabilities. Specialist leisure provision provides children with disabilities with access to the same leisure opportunities as non-disabled children, but adapted to their needs (Department for Education, 2021). According to family-carers, notable benefits of specialist leisure provision include access to specially trained staff and discrimination-free spaces (Collins et al., 2023).

Specialist leisure activities have been demonstrated to improve the emotional well-being of children with disabilities (Brajša-Žganec et al., 2010). However, the wider impacts of specialist leisure services

on the well-being of families of these children remain unclear. Therefore, we explored how specialist leisure clubs for children with disabilities impact the well-being of their family members, such as parents and siblings.

METHODOLOGY

Design

This work included an analysis of datasets generated during evaluations of specialist leisure services for children with disabilities conducted at two time periods. The evaluations used comparable qualitative methodology to generate data: the first included interviews with family-carers of children accessing a club for young people who have continuing care packages with their local health board due to complex needs arising from disability; the second included focus groups and interviews with family-carers of children accessing specialist play and youth clubs for children with a diagnosis of a disability who cannot access mainstream leisure clubs. The decision to combine data was taken as both explored the families' experiences when their children accessed specialist clubs with the same aims. The two evaluations explored the impact of the specialist leisure clubs on both the children and their family-carers, however here we are reporting an analysis of the impact on family-carers only. The impact on the children is analysed and reported elsewhere. The evaluation designs, including data collection and recording, were consistent.

Setting

Sparkle, a registered charity (1093690) in South Wales, UK, delivers specialist leisure clubs for children and young people with disabilities aged five to seventeen who cannot access mainstream leisure activities because of their complex needs. The charity works in partnership with Aneurin Bevan University Health Board Children's Centres and provides its services in a building that is co-located with health and social care. Specialist facilities include sensory rooms, rebound trampolines, bouldering walls, accessible playgrounds, and outdoor equipment designed for children with additional needs. Children attend the clubs independently of their family carers, and Sparkle employs trained leisure support staff who meet the children's physical, social, and communication needs while supporting their participation in activities. These staff members have previous experience of working with children with complex needs and complete training in safeguarding, Team Teach, safer manual handling of children, paediatric first aid, administration of medication, sign-along, and food safety.

In house training on play, communication, and personal care is provided for staff, and some also complete rebound and bouldering training so they can safely oversee use of specialist facilities. The Continuing Care club was offered every two weeks and lasted two hours for children aged five to eleven and four hours for those aged twelve to seventeen. During this club, leisure support staff provided full care for the children and young people, including personal care, medication, and specialist feeding support, and assistance with movement from wheelchairs to beanbags or to facilities such as the rebound trampoline by using hoists. Staff planned a varied programme of activities for each session, guided by the interests of the young people while also encouraging them to explore new experiences.

A wide range of activities was offered, which included arts and crafts such as making bird feeders or cards for special occasions, outdoor play using accessible playground equipment, indoor play such as passing a ball or using a remote control car, sensory play, supervised trampoline sessions, and simple cooking and baking activities such as decorating biscuits.

Sparkle Play Clubs for children aged five to eleven and Youth Clubs for those aged twelve to seventeen took place weekly and lasted either one and a half or two hours. These sessions offered a range of play activities and games that children and young people could choose from, such as drawing, messy play, sensory activities, outdoor use of the playground or other outdoor options, imaginative play with toys, and group games including parachute activities.

A typical Youth Club session included crafts such as bracelet making, group activities such as playing pool or air hockey, outdoor activities, computer games designed to encourage movement or teamwork such as dance based games, and skill building tasks including cooking.

All Sparkle clubs include enrichment sessions with external organisations, such as art, sport, music and animal encounter sessions, and activities are planned to offer variety and meet the wishes of children and young people. The needs of the children and young people varied, however the majority received 1:1 support from a Leisure Support Worker during sessions to help them engage in activities, interact with their peers, and meet any personal care, mobility, communication or behavioural support needs. Some children required two members of staff due to the complexity of their needs, while many of the young people attending youth club received 'small group' support, where one member of staff for 2–4 young people.

Participant recruitment

Participants were recruited from family-carers of children accessing Sparkle clubs. For the Continuing Care Club evaluation, family-carers of 6 children who had been accessing the club fortnightly for at least one year were invited by email and follow-up phone call; family-carers of 4 children participated (6 participants total as for some children 2 parents took part). For the play and youth clubs' evaluation, 34 family-carers had agreed to be contacted regarding participating in a focus group during a quantitative evaluation of the clubs (details reported elsewhere); following contact via email, 6 family-carers of 6 children participated.

Data collection

Interviews for the Continuing Care Club evaluation took place between June and October 2023. For the play and youth clubs' evaluation, two small focus groups (3 and 2 participants) and one interview took place during July 2024; smaller focus groups and an interview were conducted to accommodate participant availability. Interviews and focus groups were conducted by researcher 1, who is female and has a master's degree in Clinical Psychology and professional experience in the third sector conducting research using qualitative and mixed methods. This researcher was known to some participants prior to data collection due to the researcher's prior work with the charity. Data collection was supported by an Assistant Psychologist employed by the local Health Board and Psychology master's student, both male, who were unknown to participants prior to the interviews/focus groups. None of the researchers involved in data collection were involved in the delivery of the leisure clubs evaluated. Participants were invited to attend interviews/focus groups at Serennu Children's Centre; 6 attended in person, however 2 joined focus groups remotely via Microsoft Teams and interviews with 4 participants were conducted over the phone, due to participant availability. Interviews and focus groups were audio recorded using a Dictaphone and transcribed verbatim by the researchers, with any potentially identifying information removed and participants given a code number to protect their anonymity. Interviews lasted between 20 and 45 minutes (average 29 minutes) and focus groups lasted between 40 and 53 minutes (average 48 minutes).

Analysis

Data were analysed using reflexive thematic analysis (RTA) by researcher 1. RTA allowed the researcher to identify patterns across the data and generate themes which provide meaning-based interpretive stories. An inductive, semantic approach to coding and theme development was employed, generating codes and themes based on the explicit content and assumed reality of the data (Braun & Clarke, 2023).

RTA embraces researcher subjectivity, acknowledging that the researcher's own experiences, knowledge and position influences and contributes to data analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2024). Researcher 1 has worked with family-carers of children with disabilities in a research and evaluation capacity for 4 years. Primarily her work has focused on the impact of specialist leisure services on the children, however she has previously evaluated support services for family-carers and her interest in how the leisure services impact the wider family of the children who access the clubs influenced the analysis of this data. Researcher 2 has an academic interest in children's psychological disorders and experience of working directly with children and adults with autism, learning disabilities and mental health difficulties.

Researcher 1 adopted a constructionist approach to analysis, with meaning created through interaction between participants and the researcher and the researcher's interpretation of the data; it

is acknowledged that interpretation of the data by another researcher may have resulted in differing themes constructed.

Following data collection, Researcher 1 engaged in listening to audio recordings and reading transcripts to immerse herself in each family's experience, during which she identified sections of each transcript relevant to the research topic. These sections were then coded manually, noting similar and recurring words and phrases. Researcher 1 prepared a brief summary of her interpretation of each family's experiences using the initial codes and reflections on the interviews and focus groups. Initial themes were then generated from the codes and summaries, which were developed and refined into the final themes following a further review of the data. Researcher 2 was familiarised with the data during collection and transcription, and reviewed and agreed the themes generated by researcher 1.

Ethical approval

The play and youth clubs service evaluation was approved by Aneurin Bevan University Health Board Research and Development Department Research Risk Review Panel on 29th March 2023 (SE/1508-23). The same panel approved the Continuing Care service evaluation on 7th June 2023 (SE/1536-23).

RESULTS

Themes generated during analysis have been grouped into those related to the impact on the individual family-carer, the whole family, and the family's wider community.

Demographic information

Family-carers, 10 female and 2 male, of 10 children and young people took part. The children, 4 girls and 6 boys, were aged 6 to 17 years (mean 11 years, median 10 years). Children's diagnoses included autism, cerebral palsy, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, Down syndrome and rare genetic disorders; 4 of the children's diagnoses and complex needs necessitated a continuing care package with their health board. Half of the children attended a special school, while the other half attended a mainstream school with additional support, and 4 were non-speaking.

Individual: Access to respite

Participants described close relationships between family-carers and children with disabilities, however acknowledged the importance of time apart for both family-carer and child. Family-carers rarely spent any time without their child; for the majority of participants, the only time they were not caring for their child was during the school day (when they would usually be at work instead), however for some participants whose child did not attend a school setting, they were with their child '24/7'. Participants felt it was important for both family-carers and the child to have a break from this intense relationship: 'I need some kind of break because otherwise its 24/7, and he needs to be out doing stuff as well' (P2).

It's just us, there's nobody else. Even though we like [child] going to the group mostly to have fun with other children roughly around the same age, it gives us a little bit of a break as well because we rarely have any time to ourselves. When [dad] is working, I look after [child] and when I'm working, he looks after her so there's no break, it's constant. (P10a)

Despite this, great difficulty finding suitable childcare or respite opportunities was described, with participants sharing concerns regarding relying on their family members: 'People get money from the council but can't use it because they can't find people [...] no respite because you can't find people to do it' (P3).

Our parents are older now, we're really noticing that, we both work so we rely on them to take to and from school because I would not be able to rely on a childminder unless it was a specialist childminder. [...] We do rely on family members and you've got to be so mindful then to know that they've got their limits haven't they. (P4)

Typically, children without disabilities can access leisure activities independently of their parents, such as afterschool clubs, sports, creative arts lessons, and uniformed groups. These opportunities

provide a regular break for parents, however for family-carers of children with disabilities, these are not accessible unless parents stay with their child to help meet their support needs: 'Mainstream clubs, we couldn't have left her there on her own, we'd have to be there with her' (P1); 'Within a community setting I could never feel safe that somebody was there all the time to understand him, or understand his needs, so I was never able to leave him unattended at a community setting' (P5).

Individual: Taking a "guilt-free break" from caring

A specialist leisure setting allowed children with disabilities to safely access leisure activities independently of their parents, giving family-carers much needed respite time. Feelings of guilt often inhibit family-carers from allowing their child to join an activity, since entrusting their child to others creates anxieties such as a fear they will not be cared for properly, they will not be safe, or their child will not be able to communicate their needs to the carers. Crucially, participants described this short break from caring responsibilities as "guilt-free"; because their child was doing something enjoyable and were in a safe environment with staff who were able to meet their needs, family-carers were able to truly relax instead of feeling stressed or guilty for the time they are away from their child: "We have time on our own when she comes to Sparkle [...] we know she's in a safe place and we can just chill out" (P8a).

"I would say I definitely feel a bit more refreshed. So I've had a break, I don't have that guilt [...] it takes away the guilt because I know he's going there where he's enjoying it, I can then enjoy the time that I have." (P9)

Participants shared how they use this time to complete practical tasks, such as shopping and household chores, however perhaps more importantly, family-carers were able to spend time on their own well-being activities, with examples of having time for a relaxing bath or to read a book, working on personal health and fitness goals, or catching up with friends over a coffee: "I would take my son to the park, we'd go and do a food shop, we might go out for some lunch, I might go to the gym or out for a run" (P9); "It gives us respite to go shopping or go for a coffee" (P1).

Family: Strengthening relationships within the family

Participants were very open about how relationships between parents can become strained due to a lack of quality time together, pressures of caring, and overwhelming working and caring schedules.

"Ever since we've had [child], we feel like Mummy and Daddy, not [name] and [name]. We feel like an appendage to her rather than individuals anymore. [...] we've become quite frayed around the edges and there's been a couple of times where we've felt like we're hanging onto our relationship by bare fingers and it hasn't always been like that. I think back and people need to do things together and we haven't really had that chance." (P10b)

Having a regular opportunity to spend time together and reconnect seemed to strengthen relationships between parents. The process of adapting to their child's disability is recognised as a form of grieving, which parents acknowledged. The opportunity for their child to access a specialist club gave them a sense of belonging, while accepting their child's difference. Likewise, regular attendance by their child at the club has the potential to improve the Family Sense of Coherence (FSOC), as highlighted by carers reporting positive experiences, and improved family well-being, enhancing their ability to be more confident in developing their resources as a family.

"We like to do stuff as a family so it's really important for us to have quality time and for me and my husband to have quality time just me and him, to just go and do stress-free things like going to the supermarket and doing stuff together because we have to do a lot of stuff separately when [child] is with us." (P9)

"Because [child] relies on me and my husband so much there's no let up, it's that hour and a half a week which I think me and my husband really look forward to as well just to say 'that's our time'." (P5)

Caring for a child with complex needs can also affect relationships between parents and other children in the household. Participants shared how their child with a disability often requires greater attention than even younger children in the household, which can result in siblings feeling left out or "less special": "Even though they're younger, [child] still needs more of my attention, so just to

know that we have that time where we can plan something without him" (P6); "She's so young to process all of that [...] I think sometimes she needs a bit of a boost. She was saying to me the other day 'I'm not special like [child] because [child] is autistic'" (P4).

The time afforded to family-carers by the specialist leisure clubs allowed parents and siblings to spend quality time together to strengthen their relationship and ensure the emotional needs of other children in the household are met. Often, participants described being able to access activities which their child with a disability would not be able to take part in, therefore creating equity for the whole family.

"[Sibling] loves to be out and about, he's very busy. [Child] is in a wheelchair so she's quite staged, she's not able to join in those activities so it's nice for [sibling] to have opportunities to go to the park and have a run around and we can run with him rather than 'oh you can't go there because I can't run with [child] in her chair'. So it does do us all good for her to have that time where she can, we know she's perfectly safe and we can be off doing something a bit manic that we can't normally do or take [sibling] out for lunch [...] we try to do something with [sibling] that's not accessible for [child] or not really fair for her to partake. She'd just be sitting watching which is not fair." (P7)

Family: Easing distress for parents and siblings

The specialist leisure clubs reduced distress for family-carers, who shared that their concerns regarding their child's well-being have been relieved thanks to their child's improved mood following club sessions and their child enjoying the experiences offered to them: "Because [child] is happy I feel like everything is falling into place [...] all my other goals, it's not as important to me anymore, his well-being is most important" (P6).

A few participants noted how difficult it can be to keep their child occupied with stimulating activities at home, however the clubs provided greater opportunities for their child and participants shared the benefits of these to their home lives, such as improved mood and better sleep following a session: "It's constantly trying to come up with things that he's prepared to do [...] that's one opportunity to be out of the house, have a nice time, he'll be in a better mood when he comes back" (P2).

"He's definitely sleeping much better and it's definitely down to being stimulated and we can't do that at home all the time, because just life is, it moves quickly, and when we're at home there's stuff that always needs doing, cooking and cleaning and doing homework, so it's really difficult to try and stimulate him all the time. When he's going to club, like I said it takes away that guilt, you know he's then done something where he's been stimulated which has a major impact on other things like sleep." (P9)

Their child being in a positive mood and displaying signs of improved well-being has a knock-on impact on mood and well-being of family-carers.

"It's just wonderful to see [my child] so happy and enjoying something that's separate, that's specifically for [her] and having that opportunity. There are so many things that [she] can't access, because she's got so many complex needs. [...] She has such a wonderful time and that means the world to all of us because she's happy, she's getting these experiences and I mean it's good for our mental well-being that we know that she's in a safe place and she's happy doing things she enjoys and getting opportunities to try new things that we wouldn't have thought of." (P7)

Participants shared how both adults and children in the family have felt distressed due to concerns for their child or sibling's well-being, with fears regarding their social interactions and overall happiness. However, the specialist nature of the leisure activities, where the children are understood and supported, helped ease this distress.

"It does have a massive impact on the family and I think also for the siblings. I think [my daughter] really worries about [child] and I think for her to know that he's able to go somewhere where he is listened to, where he is able to communicate with people, where he is supported and he does feel comfortable, you know she then takes great pride in that as well." (P5)

"As a parent you are faced with 'your child has a difference, they're going to have a lifelong difficulty', it's just horrendous for you because all you care about is that your child is happy and well.

[...] yes life is different to maybe what you imagined it was going to be like, but actually this is wonderful too. I think that really encompasses what Sparkle is really." (P4)

Community: Meeting other families and making connections

While the specialist leisure clubs aimed to promote social interaction among the children, some participants reported a similar result for family-carers. One participant shared how they had formed their own friendship group since their child started accessing, as they were able to meet other family-carers with whom they shared similar experiences.

"Before [we] joined that club I didn't have any friends to go anywhere with, so now we've got a WhatsApp group and we talk all the time [...] we meet up outside, and because they have kids in the same age bracket and same kind of situation, they understand it you know" (P3)

The opportunity to form supportive friendships thanks to the specialist leisure clubs had a resounding positive impact on family-carer well-being, and other participants shared how they felt they would benefit from more opportunities to connect with other family-carers. Some felt drop-off and pick-up times did not provide ample opportunities to engage with others and suggested other ways to facilitate those connections being made, such as virtual groups or family-carer sessions alongside club sessions: "I suppose if [a parent/carer group] was happening at the time [child] was at the club I would probably attend" (P1).

"Maybe if we just had a Facebook group that even if a couple of us wanted the children to get together and we just get together as a group outside of Sparkle, say we'll go to the park but as a family, as a unit." (P5)

As well as the specialist leisure clubs, families were able to access other services delivered by the charity, such as family support services, family activities and events. This holistic approach also meant families could meet and connect with others who shared similar experiences, for example via support groups and events: "It was really nice at the summer fete because [my husband] met up with some of the other dads" (P6); "I think having everything here, all the services and then you know the events, it just means you're supported as a family because you can have these opportunities which we wouldn't necessarily have" (P4).

Community: Understanding and inclusion

It was very common for participants to share feelings of isolation and anxiety, as they felt "other" people couldn't understand their lives or their child's needs: "You're just totally isolated because people don't get it, they don't understand" (P2). Both children and family-carers felt different to their friends or peers at school, however by accessing a specialist setting they felt a sense of community and understanding: "My friends, they wouldn't understand because they try to compare it to their child which is totally different, but at [Sparkle] they understand you" (P6); "With school, he's like 'nobody's like me, I don't belong here', we've had lots of that. [...] So I think that's the level of community that he actually feels like he belongs somewhere." (P4).

The setting and a community of people with similar life experiences helped participants feel safe. "You can come here and you know that it's a safe area and that lots of people you're going to meet here are going to be people that you've got similarities with so you feel relaxed here. It's just about that feeling of safety." (P4)

This feeling of safety and community allowed family-carers and children to be themselves, without having to "mask", and promoted feelings of inclusion: "He clearly knows when he comes into this place that he can be completely himself and I think that's lovely. That's nothing I've done, Sparkle have created that" (P6).

"My husband is a typical blokey bloke so he's not kind of wanting to talk to lots of other people, however he said when we got home 'I felt included', he felt like he actually belonged and he didn't have to be separate." (P5)

DISCUSSION

The aim of this evaluation was to explore how specialist leisure clubs for children with disabilities impact the well-being of their family members, such as parents and siblings. At an individual level, specialist leisure clubs for children with disabilities equip family-carers with respite opportunities which they struggle to source elsewhere, allowing them to take a break from caring responsibilities which, crucially, is "guilt-free" as their child is safe and taking part in enjoyable activities. For the whole family, this eases distress related to concerns for the child's social and emotional well-being, and parents and siblings benefit from the child being in a positive mood following the stimulation of club sessions. Parents and siblings also gain quality time together while the child is accessing the leisure club, helping strengthen relationships. In addition to their home life, findings suggest access to the leisure clubs creates a community for these families, who are able to meet others with similar lived experiences and experience understanding and inclusion, without fear of judgement.

Our findings detailing difficulties accessing respite echo those from research conducted over 15 years ago. Mansell and Wilson (2009) conducted a survey and focus groups among members of a parent and carer federation to explore respite experiences of family-carers of children and adults with learning disabilities. This highlighted that only 43% of carers received any respite care, and participants felt information about respite was not provided by their local authorities due to a lack of available services, rather than due to ineligibility. In addition to structural barriers to respite, lack of appropriate facilities, funding shortfall etc., the carers themselves may exhibit complex decision-making processes which become barriers to taking up respite opportunities offered. An exploration of this by Dubois et al. (2023) identified emotional barriers preventing carers of children with complex needs availing of respite opportunities, which include concerns about taking up a space that another child may need more than theirs, the need to provide emotional support to carers whose child does avail of a respite activity, guilt and mental burden such that they do not accept the need for respite until they are at the point of mental and physical exhaustion.

Parents of children with disability often experience guilt from the time of diagnosis, which may be a combination of disappointment, anger or hostility towards the child, which cause further negative emotions. Rosenzweig (1978) has classified the reactions to frustration into three categories: intropunitive reaction, anger and frustration is directed towards the "self" which prevents their actualisation, such that they manifest as guilt and regret; extrapunitive reaction, whereby the anger and hostility is directed at others, which allows an expression of the hostile feelings; impunitive reaction, whereby feelings of guilt are slight, leading to compromise and sublimation, although this latter response relies on strong self-esteem.

The frequent reference to "guilt free" respite among our carers is consistent with them recognising their need to have a period away from their caring responsibilities, consistent with avoidance-type behaviours in emotion focused coping, as described by Lazarus and Folkman (1984). Among our group, the carers cannot change their situation due to their child's lifelong disability, and they frequently reported primary appraisals of this stress by recognising all the aspects that cause it, such as being unable to provide their child with the stimulation they need, having no one else to help care for their child, and no time for the carers to spend with one another, as described by: "It's just us, there's nobody else. Even though we like [child] going to the group mostly to have fun with other children roughly around the same age, it gives us a little bit of a break as well because we rarely have any time to ourselves. When [dad] is working, I look after [child] and when I'm working, he looks after her so there's no break, it's constant. (P10a)". The provision of this specialist leisure club enabled carers to cope by employing a secondary appraisal technique of avoidance, i.e. engaging in their own activities while their child is at club. However, it is clearly important to the parents own mental well-being that their child is enjoying a tailor-made activity while they take this break, which alleviates their own perceived guilt at availing of the respite opportunity. During these interviews they have reflected on the impact of this strategy (re-appraisal) by identifying how the child's attendance at club has benefited them as a family. In this way the respite provided by the Sparkle clubs can be perceived as an outcome experienced by the carers, rather than as an operational framing, as defined by Chappell et al. (2001). Furthermore, case studies conducted by Hartrey and Wells (2003) revealed that family-carers of children with disabilities experience strong emotional connections with their child and a level of attachment which results in feelings of guilt when they do access respite support. It is therefore key that respite opportunities provide safe and enjoyable activities for the children, to help alleviate feelings of guilt for family-carers and allow them to take a meaningful break from caring responsibilities. This emotion came out strongly within our evaluation,

where the benefits of a specialist setting and highly trained staff who can ensure the children get the maximum enjoyment from their sessions relieved the family-carers of guilt. Relinquishing control around the care of their disabled child can be emotionally fraught for family-carers, as can an acknowledgement that they need a break. Thus, the fact that the children in our study enjoyed their sessions, and were provided with the level of trained support they need to maximise their engagement, helps to alleviate this for carers.

Caring for a child with complex needs can place a strain on relationships within the family. Mothers have acknowledged that their relationship with their child with complex needs is different to relationships with their other children, due to their level of dependence (Hartrey & Wells, 2003), and a systematic review, including 26 studies and 3,308 parents of children with autism, and a meta-analysis of 7 studies, found parents of children with autism experienced lower relationship satisfaction than parents of children without a disability, with a clear need for support to help parents maintain their relationships (Wilkes-Gillan & Bourke-Taylor, 2017). Our findings suggest the respite time provided by specialist leisure clubs for children with disabilities can help strengthen these relationships, for example by allowing parents and siblings to take part in activities the family would usually avoid due to inaccessibility, but are comfortable engaging in when their child with complex needs is also enjoying their own dedicated activities tailored to their needs. Similarly, previous research has found that siblings of children with disabilities tend to miss out on social activities due to caring demands on the family; however respite opportunities can open up these activities for families (Hartrey & Wells, 2003). Coping is a process that is characterised by dynamic processes and change, and as such depends on continuous appraisal and reappraisal of the changing relationship between the individual and their environment (Gagani et al., 2016; Steele & Fitch, 1996). From a Family Systems Perspective, a variety of coping strategies are needed for families of disabled children, to maintain the balance between their resources and the demands placed on them. Trute and Hauch (1988) define adaptation to a child with a disability as being a transactional process, characterised by reciprocal affection between the child and their family, which influences the child's emotional development as well as the social climate within the family. In our study carers commented on the benefits not only from their disabled child engaging in an activity they enjoyed, but that this improved their mood on returning to the family home, while family members themselves have enjoyed their own activities, which improves the family's well-being and functioning, despite the degree of their child's disability. Trute and Hauch also emphasise that a positive adaptation by families to a disabled child is enhanced by their skilful use of friendship network resources, and the provision of these specialist leisure clubs provides carers with these potential networks, which they comment on as a positive aspect of the provision.

Findings from our evaluation suggest the specialist leisure clubs help family-carers connect with other families, facilitating social inclusion and an understanding community. Peer support is important to families of children with disabilities; a review of existing research on peer support networks for these families, excluding groups facilitated by "professionals" or peer groups which include families without children with disabilities, found that shared experiences and feelings of equality in their relationships with other parents in the group allowed family-carers to share honestly and without fear of judgement (Chakraborti et al., 2021). The same review found these peer support networks provided a sense of security and belonging for family-carers, as well as reduced social isolation for the whole family. The availability of appropriate childcare is a barrier to accessing peer support for these family-carers, however play-based childcare during peer support sessions helps promote access (Hammarberg et al., 2014), which was echoed in our findings, as parents were more likely to access peer support while their child attended these club sessions. Peer support from others whose child has disabilities not only promotes social engagement, but it can also promote cognitive adaptation to emerging situations their child may face (Lo, 2010).

Limitations of this evaluation include the low uptake by family-carers of children attending play and youth clubs to the invitation to participate, with only 18% of those who agreed to be contacted regarding the evaluation participating. While the experiences of those included in the evaluation are valid, differing experiences and points of view may have been missed due to low uptake. The small sample size also lacked diversity, and it is acknowledged that participants with different backgrounds and life experiences may have contributed alternative views and experiences. However, it is recognised that family-carers of children with disabilities are extremely time poor, thus this low uptake may not be surprising. Researcher 1, who conducted the data analysis, is employed by the charity which delivers the specialist leisure clubs, therefore it could be argued that there is the potential for bias towards positive aspects of the clubs in the results. However, this potential bias was

reduced by collaborating with external researchers during data collection and synthesis. A negative finding was observed relating to the "drop off" and "pick up" times, which parents felt inhibited their ability to connect with other parents, and suggested that a "family-carer" activity running in parallel with the child's session could be helpful. Likewise, it was proposed that a social media network group for carers could facilitate further group activities for families. Although few negative impacts of the leisure clubs were reported in this analysis, this may be due to sample-bias during recruitment; researchers were only able to recruit participants from those currently accessing the service, and it is possible that those who no longer accessed may have had negative experiences.

The findings of this evaluation demonstrate the value of specialist leisure activities for families of children with complex disabilities, further to the direct benefits for the children themselves. Given the challenges faced by these families, particularly related to difficulties sourcing appropriate respite care, our findings indicate that this speciality provision, independent of family-carers, has the potential to improve family resilience, and should help to inform policymakers and those commissioning and designing respite and support services for this group.

CONCLUSION

This evaluation has demonstrated several benefits of specialist leisure provision for children with disabilities on the well-being of the family. At an individual level, specialist provisions offered respite time for family-carers which, crucially, is "guilt-free", allowing them to relax and complete tasks they would not otherwise have time for. At the family level, specialist leisure strengthened familial relationships and eased concerns regarding the child's emotional well-being. Specialist leisure also developed a sense of community and inclusion among family-carers, allowing them to make connections, despite this not being a direct aim of the clubs. The findings of this evaluation are positive and further work on using specialist leisure clubs as respite services is warranted, particularly as there is a dearth of literature on interventions that improve coping and positive family functioning among carers of disabled children.

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